

ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS IN FORECASTING MINIMUM TEMPERATURE

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Forecasting the minimum temperature (T_{min}) is one of the most important operational practices carried out by Meteorological Services worldwide. The great interest in developing methods for more accurate predictions has led to the invention of several such methods of which the most commonly used can be considered to fall into three groups.

In the first group are *physical* methods utilizing the laws of radiation, Bagdonas et. al. (1). However, the complexity of the process of nocturnal cooling renders such methods difficult to manipulate and their practical application is limited. The second group comprises *statistical-empirical* methods that are basically mathematical relationships fitted to archived meteorological data by means of a curve fitting procedure, Boyden (2), Craddock and Pritchard (3), and Michaelides (4). Because such relationships are relatively easy to establish, the techniques in this group have been widely used for many decades. With the arrival of numerical weather modeling, a third group of *numerical-statistical* methods has evolved which have progressively been adopted by many Meteorological Services (e.g. Klein et. al. (5), Kelley et. al. (6), and Lemcke and Kruijzinga (7)). In this approach, T_{min} is statistically linked with archived observed or simulated meteorological parameters. Numerical model products are subsequently used as input to obtain a temperature forecast. Widespread use of this technique is still restricted by the availability of numerical weather prediction products.

Expert systems have recently been introduced in meteorology with promising results regarding the diagnosis and the prediction of certain weather elements, Moninger (8), and Peak and Tag (9). In this study, an attempt is made to tackle the problem of minimum temperature forecasting using artificial neural networks.

MATERIAL

The set of raw data involved in this work has been extracted from the synoptic meteorological observations recorded at three-hour intervals at Larnaca Airport, Cyprus (34° 52' 52" N, 33° 37' 32" E). From each one of the eight sets of observations available daily, the following elements have been extracted:

- total cloud cover [TC]
- eastward wind component [W1]
- northward wind component [W2]
- visibility [VI]
- present weather condition [PW]
- atmospheric pressure [AP]
- dry-bulb temperature [DB]
- wet-bulb temperature [WB] and
- low cloud cover [LC].

Besides these records,

- astronomical day length [DL] and
- observed minimum temperature of the previous night [PM]

were used for forming the input data vector to the neural network. Thus, the complete set of data available to describe one day consists of 74 parameter values (8 sets of 9 records + DL + PM). A day is considered to start at 2100 GMT and end at 1800 GMT (local time = GMT + 2 hours).

In the present study, a total of 141 days of the winter and spring of 1984 were used for training and evaluating the forecasting models. Of these days, 103 were randomly selected and used for training, and the rest 38 days were used for testing the models.

LEARNING ALGORITHM

Neural network training algorithms have made possible the practical use of multilayer perceptron architectures. The algorithm under study, is the back propagation, by Rumelhart et. al. (10). The basic idea of this method is the utilization of a non-linear perceptron-like system, capable of making decisions. This is achieved by minimizing the least-mean-square (LMS) error. The LMS is the error between the actual output of the multilayer feed-forward perceptron and the desired output. For meeting this criterion, the derivative of the error function with respect to any weight in the network is computed and is applied for adapting the corresponding weight(s) as follows:

$$\Delta w_{ij} = -k \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

An equivalent computational formula of the above that is used recursively, starting at the output nodes for adjusting the weights is:

$$w_{ij}(t+1) - w_{ij}(t) = n \delta_j x_i' \quad (2)$$

Where $w_{ij}(t)$ is the weight from hidden node j or from an input node j at time t , x_i' is either the output of node j or is an input, n is the learning rate (gain) of the net, and δ_j is the error term for node j .

The learning rate of the algorithm as shown in the above equation may speed up the learning process. There is a possibility however, that undesirable oscillations may be introduced. This possibility can be reduced by introducing an extra term as follows:

$$w_{ij}(t+1) - w_{ij}(t) = n \delta_j x_i' + \alpha (w_{ij}(t) - w_{ij}(t-1)) \quad (3)$$

In the above equation the introduced constant α is called the momentum term that achieves faster convergence by smoothing weight changes.

The back propagation training algorithm requires that the derivative of the activation function exists. The continuous differentiable non-linear function that suffices the above, known as the logistic activation function is given by:

$$f(x_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(x_i - \theta)}} \quad (4)$$

which has a sigmoidal shape with threshold level θ . The term x_i represents the summation of inputs (P_j) to the i th unit and it is determined by:

$$x_i = \sum w_{ij} P_j + \theta_i \quad (5)$$

ANN FORECASTING MODELS / DISCUSSION

The back propagation training algorithm, was used for building the investigated artificial neural network (ANN) models. Table 1 shows all the ANN models that were trained with the data from 103 of the 141 available days, and tested with the data of the remaining 38 days. For all the examined models the gain η , and the momentum α , were chosen to be 0.01 and 0.9 respectively.

For each model the number of inputs (the first number shown by the architecture in Table 1) is determined by the number of parameters that are used for training the model. The number of units in the first and the second hidden layers of the model are represented by the second and the third number of the architecture, respectively. These numbers were chosen empirically. The number of outputs was chosen to be forty for all the models. The forty outputs represent the temperature range -5°C to +15°C with 0.5°C intervals, that form the available classes of the models. The accuracy can increase or decrease by narrowing or widening the temperature interval. The temperature range can be increased, if required by increasing the output classes.

Most of the models learned the training set very well as suggested by the total sum of squares (TSS). TSS is defined as the sum of the squared difference between the expected and the calculated output for all cases (days) in the training cycle (one epoch). TSS is the principal measure of performance in the back propagation training algorithm. Models with TSS near unity learned with 100% yield the training set. Models 4,5 and 7 achieved learning with 80, 94 and 96% yield, respectively. These models produced comparable results with the rest of the models in spite of the not so successful learning of the training data.

The forecasting yield, shown on Table 1, is a measure of the success of a model during the testing (evaluation) phase. The percentage of days in the testing set of data for which the minimum temperature was successfully forecasted, is defined as the forecasting yield of a model. This forecasting yield is given for temperature confidence ranges: ± 0.5 , ± 1.0 , ± 2.0 , and ± 3.0 °C, as given in Table 1. It is obvious that, an increase of the temperature confidence range will increase the forecasting yield, at the expense of accuracy.

Models 1,2 and 3 have been trained by using the complete set of daily meteorological input, but they differ in the architecture. The forecasting yield associated with the temperature confidence range ± 3.0 °C varied from 50 to 68%. The best performance is achieved with model 3, that has the smallest architecture. The results obtained here are comparable to the results obtained by using a statistical/empirical method for the same weather station and for the same time period, Michaelides (6).

Trying to assess the significance of the various input parameters on the performance of the models, it has been decided to build a series of different models based on reduced feature sets. The models numbered 4 to 11 are based on the complete set of daily meteorological data, namely from 2100 previous day to 1800 GMT on going day. The forecasting yield associated with the range ± 0.5 °C varies from 16 to 24%, whereas, that associated with the range ± 3.0 °C varies from 42 to 66%. This is an almost three-fold increase of the forecasting yield. Model 4 makes use of PW and PM; model 5 is based on these two elements and DB and WB. This increase of the number of input parameters results in a decrease of the forecasting yield associated with the ranges ± 0.5 and ± 1.0 °C and an increase of the yield associated with ranges ± 2.0 and ± 3.0 °C. Further expansion of the basis of the models by adding elements W1 and W2, namely model 11, exhibits a general tendency for reduced yields.

Models 6 to 11 have a common basis of features W1, W2, DB and WB. Expansion of this base by adding more parameters, does not necessarily improve the forecasting yield. It is worth mentioning that for the range ± 3.0 °C, the best performing model in this group of models, model 5, produces a 66% forecasting yield. This forecasting yield is nearly equal to that produced by model 3, that appears to have the best performance, considering the models that make use of the complete feature set.

TABLE 1- ANN models and results.

MODEL	ARCHITECTURE	EPOCHS	TSS	FORECASTING YIELD %				PARAMETERS											
				± 0.5 °C	± 1.0 °C	± 2.0 °C	± 3.0 °C	TC	W1	W2	VI	PW	AP	DB	WB	LC	DL	PM	
1	74-120-160-40	290	0.9	21	32	45	53	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	74-80-120-40	410	0.9	16	29	45	50	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3	74-40-60-40	670	2.5	18	37	60	68	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4	9-16-32-40	8060	30.6	24	32	39	53					✓							
5	25-40-60-40	2460	7.3	21	29	47	66					✓		✓	✓				✓
6	32-40-80-40	4070	5.0	24	29	47	50		✓	✓				✓	✓				
7	48-60-100-40	431	0.9	18	26	37	42	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓			
8	33-40-80-40	4020	2.0	18	29	53	58		✓	✓				✓	✓				✓
9	34-40-80-40	587	0.9	16	32	47	55		✓	✓				✓	✓			✓	✓
10	41-50-100-40	4180	3.0	18	29	50	60		✓	✓				✓	✓				✓
11	41-50-100-40	453	0.9	24	26	39	55		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓				✓
12	29-40-80-40	1330	2.2	21	39	50	58		✓	✓				✓	✓				✓
13	36-50-100-40	1100	0.9	21	32	42	53		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓				✓

All the above models are designed to produce a forecast when all the meteorological data become available at 1800 GMT. However, a minimum temperature prediction is very often required before this time. Bearing this in mind, models that can make use of data available at an earlier time, were constructed. Such models based on data from 2100 to 1500 GMT are numbered 12 and 13, as shown in Table 1. Models 12 and 13 make use of the same feature sets as models 8 and 11, respectively. Using model 12 produces slightly better forecasting yields than model 8 for small temperature confidence ranges but it does not have any significant impact for large temperature confidence ranges. Model 13 gives a slightly better performance than model 11 in the confidence ranges ± 1.0 and $\pm 2.0^\circ\text{C}$; and a slightly worse performance for the confidence range $\pm 3.0^\circ\text{C}$.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The usefulness of ANN models in forecasting the minimum temperature was investigated. The highest yield was found to be 24, 39, 60 and 68% for the range ± 0.5 , ± 1.0 , ± 2.0 and $\pm 3.0^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Although the results presented in this work are preliminary, it is inferred that the introduced method can claim a place in practical applications. The present method requires a commonly available meteorological data base without any additional experimental requirements. Also, once the models are developed, the operational application of the method requires limited computational resources. The above render the method advantageous over other methods that demand specific experimental designs to generate the data sets that require extensive computational resources.

The present work was carried out using a limited number of data. Further work is needed to exploit the full capacity of ANN models in meteorological forecasting. Such endeavour will certainly require a larger data base.

In this study, the back propagation algorithm as it has been proposed by Rumelhart et al. (10) was used. This method has a number of inherited limitations: heavy computational requirements, also the non existence of ANN design methodologies for deciding the values of learning coefficient η , and the momentum coefficient α . It has recently been demonstrated by Charalambous (11) that the performance of the conjugate gradient back propagation (CGBP) is superior to that of the standard back propagation algorithm. Future work will investigate the application of the CGBP algorithm in training ANN models for forecasting T_{\min} .

Finally, it must be clarified that the technique presented here is strictly site specific. This implies that additional neural network models must be build for different localities.

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